

EVALUATION OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITIES OF SOME SELECTED POWDERED FOOD PRODUCTS AND THEIR MIXTURES

Ogunleye, I.O. and Olatoyinbo, S.F.

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ado Ekiti, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This paper reports on the experimental determination of the thermal conductivities of some selected powdered food stuffs and their mixtures. The foodstuffs considered are: guinea corn flour, rice flour, maize flour, beans flour, cassava flour and yam flour. One to one mixtures of these foodstuffs were made in equal ratios to give mixtures of rice and beans flour, cassava and guinea corn flour and yam and cassava flour. Lee's Disc Apparatus was used for this investigation and the average thermal conductivities ('k' values) of the foodstuff samples are 0.2766 W/m °C, 0.2873 W/m°C, 0.3112W/m°C, 0.3410W/m°C, 0.3491W/m°C and 0.3526W/m°C respectively. The results obtained for the mixtures are 0.2706 W/m⁰C, 0.2964 W/m⁰C and 0.3112 W/m⁰C respectively. It is observed that the thermal conductivity of finer particle flours is higher than the coarse flours and the 'k' values of the mixtures are characteristically lower compared to that of the individual constituents of these mixtures.

KEYWORDS: Thermal, Conductivity, powered, foodstuffs, mixture

INTRODUCTION

Predominant among the food crops grown in tropical countries like Nigeria, most parts of West Africa, certain parts of South-America and Asia, includes: yam, cassava, maize, rice, beans and guinea corn or sorghum; see Kirk (1966). These local food stuffs are consumed either in their natural form after cooking as the case may be or are processed into various food products, including flour.

Spoilage is wholly or partly eliminated by processing these foodstuffs into various food products like flour. Processed food crops in flours form have added advantages which include: the ease of storage, longer shelf life, less prone to biochemical changes during storage enhancement in detoxifying the products and in preservation of their nutritional values to a large extent. According to Oyenuga (1968) and Asiedu (1989), Food products in flour form have the potentials for higher and better economic values and importance in large-scale production and export. In powdery form, the foodstuffs may be useful as engineering materials for insulation.

Thermal conductivities in foods have been studied by many authors, among which are Odigboh (1978), Mohsein (1980), Massey and Sunderland (1967), Poppendiels et al (1966), Rahman (1991) and Drouzez and Saravacos (1988) The modifications of five principal methods: the concentric cylinder method, the concentric sphere method, the parallel plate method, the thermal diffusing method, the line source technique were used for the studies. A review of the literatures indicate that the modifications of the parallel plate method, the thermal diffusing method and the line source technique are the approaches used most frequently for the determination and calculation of thermal conductivity in food/food products.

Conductivity probe and fitch apparatus which involve transient heat flow through the test material were used by Odigboh (1978) to determine the thermal conductivities, ('K' value) of various food materials like rice, yam, and beef. The source, stage of maturity, variety, history of landing, processing and storage of materials were recorded wherever applicable. The materials were also sufficiently characterized with

respect to their physical properties, moisture content, density and porosity. The thermal conductivity was determined at several levels of principal characterizing properties of the food materials. Some of the results obtained are presented in Tables 1 and 2

Table 1: Some 'K' Values determined with Thermal Conductivity probe method for various Nigerian Foods in Odigboh (1978)

Material	Moisture Content	Main Temperature (°c)	K (w/mk)
	13.9	65.0	0.290
Milled Rice Bulb density	20.25	42.0	0.173
	20.25	50.1	0.215
	20.25	57.1	0.270
	20.25	60.1	0.299
	29.45	62.3	0.310
Yam (Diyam)	59.00	42.7	0.521
	59.00	47.0	0.551
	59.00	52.8	0.581
	59.00	59.5	0.603
Yam (aga)	59.00	64.0	0.603
Yam (Jiutura)	63.5	59.6	0.722
	58.5	60.5	0.603

Table 2: Some 'k' values determined with Modified Fitch Apparatus for various Nigerian Food Materials in Odigboh (1978)

Materials	Moisture Content	Initial Temperature of Material	K (WM ⁻¹ K ⁻¹) at that Source Temperature		
			50°c	70°c	97°c
Yam (Obiora) (Middle Segment)	50.55	10	0.445	0.530	0.581
	50.55	25	0.468	0.492	0.603
	50.55	33	0.512	0.563	0.637
Yam (Aga) (Middle Segment)	56.3	12	0.547	0.611	0.621
	56.3	28	0.602	0.655	0.704
	56.3	35	0.623	0.676	0.714
Milled Rice Bulk Density 870kg/m ³	13.9	12	0.073	0.075	0.087
	13.9	27	0.069	0.810	0.093
	29.45	10	0.126	0.307	0.298
	13.9	29	0.201	0.198	0.205
Fresh (raw) Leon beef	74.18	12	0.483	0.514	-
	74.18	27	0.508	0.516	-
	74.18	34	0.502	0.522	-
Boiled Beef	70.47	10	0.438	0.446	-
	70.47	25	0.413	0.455	-
	70.47	35	0.505	0.510	-

Modern engineering technology in thermal conductivity measurements are advancing with greater accuracy equipment. One of such systems allows rapid and simultaneous conductivity, resistivity and diffusivity

measurements including liquid samples; see Balasubramaniam and Bowman (1977) and Bowman and Balasubramaniam(1976). The system consists of an hand-held readout and a single needle sensor. The single-needle sensor consists of a stainless steel needle containing a heater and thermistor. The thermal conductivity is calculated by monitoring the dissipation of heat versus time given a known voltage applied. This new thermal properties system provides rapid, accurate and economic means for measuring not only the thermal conductivity but also the thermal diffusivity of selected foods and soils, including liquid.

This paper present the application of Lee Disc apparatus for the determination of thermal conductivity of some tropical food products in flour forms. The determination of this property helps to ascertain the suitability of these food products as engineering material for insulation purposes.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Samples of dried grains of polished rice, guinea corn (brown) maize, cowpea and sliced tubers of cassava and white yam were obtained and ground to flour. The experimental determination of the thermal conductivities of the above granular food products was carried out using the Lee's Disc apparatus method (See Figure 1).

Figure 1: Experimental Set up of Lees Disc Apparatus for determination of Thermal Conductivity

This apparatus consists of an electric stove (controllable heat source), steam flask (containing the water being heated), a steam chest (receiving steam from steam flask and indirectly heating the food specimen), bad conductor disc 'B' (with a circular cross-section which contains and forms boundary for the granular foods within), rubber hose (conveying steam from steam flask to steam chest), and suspended brass plate disc C (holding test samples)

The Lee's apparatus was set-up and arranged as shown Figure 1. The brass plate, disc C is suspended from the adjustable ring holder attached to a tripod stand. The bad conductor, disc B is placed on disc C filled with granular food which is compacted to the height/depth of the disc B. The steam chest was placed with its base over disc B and was connected to the steam flask, which is heated by a controllable heat source. The thermometer, T_1 and T_2 were carefully placed in the holes provided on the steam chest and on brass disc C respectively. The final temperatures, T_1 and T_2 , were taken and recorded when steady state (constant temperature) condition was attained. The experiment was repeated for the entire food samples and their mixtures and their respective values of T_1 and T_2 were also recorded.

After steady state condition was achieved, the rate of cooling of the bras plate, disc C is recorded using a stop watch for twenty (20) minutes. The slope of the curve, temperature $T(^{\circ}\text{C})$ versus time (s) of steady state, T_2 will equal to the cooling rate of disc C. Therefore, the heat loss per second (W) at this temperature is given by

$$W = m \cdot c \cdot g \text{ ----- (1)}$$

where g = cooling rate of bad conductor, circular disc B.

The conditions become similar to that in which heat passes from surface of the steam chest through circular disc B to brass disc C

Thus, if the faces of disc B are at $T_1^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_2^\circ\text{C}$ respectively, then

$$mcg = -KA \frac{dT}{dx} = \frac{-K\pi d^2(T_1 - T_2)}{4x}$$

$$K = \frac{4mcgx}{\pi d^2 (T_2 - T_1)} \text{ ----- (2)}$$

where m = mass of brass disc C

c = specific heat capacity of brass disc C

d = internal diameter of disc B

x = thickness of disc B

g = cooling rate of brass plate, disc C

T_1 and T_2 = Temperatures of the two faces of disc B

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The steady temperatures of steam chest and the brass plate disc C, T_1 and T_2 for all the experiments carried out are presented in Table 3 and Table 4. A typical cooling rate curve for brass plate disc C is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Typical Cooling Rate Curve of Brass Plate Disc C

By direct measurement and from Tables of properties of metals, the following constants were obtained

$$m = 1.015\text{kg}; X = 0.00322\text{m}; d = 0.068\text{m}; c = 380 \text{ J/kg } ^\circ\text{C}$$

From Figure 2, the slope g, was obtained as

$$g = -0.0182 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C/s}$$

Using these data in equation (2) the K-value for rice flour for example is evaluated as

$$K = \frac{4x (1.015) \times (380) \times (-0.0182) \times (0.00322)}{(3.141592654) \times (0.068)^2 (T_2 - T_1)}$$

$$= \frac{-6.2240}{T_2 - T_1}$$

From Table 3 for rice flour, $T_2 - T_1 = -20^\circ\text{C}$

Hence, $K = 0.3112 \text{ w/m}^0\text{c}$

This analysis was repeated for all other samples and the average k-value for the samples are presented in Table 3 and the K-values for their mixtures are shown in Table 4. Figure 3 depicts the various thermal conductivities for the flours in a bar chart. Yam flour has the highest K-value followed by cassava flour. Guinea corn has the least k-value. Figure 4 compares the thermal conductivities of the mixtures. Mixtures of yam and cassava flour have the highest k-value and the least is rice and beans mixture. Figure 5 shows a typical comparison of the k-values of the individual constituent flour and their mixture. The k-value obtained for the mixture is comparatively less than that obtained for the individual constituent flour.

Table 3: Average values of determined K-values for powered food products

Specimen	T ₁ (⁰ C) Temperature of Steam chest	T ₂ Temperature (⁰ C) of Brass plate disc C	K (W/m ⁰ C) Thermal Conductivity	K (W/m ⁰ C) Mean Thermal Conductivity
Rice flour	97	77	0.3112	0.2873
	95	75	0.3112	
	97	71	0.2396	
Cassava Flour	97	79.5	0.3557	0.3491
	98	80	0.3458	
	97	80	0.3458	
Maize flour	96	76	0.3112	0.3112
	97	77	0.3112	
	98	78	0.3112	
Beans Flour	96	78	0.3458	0.3410
	95	78	0.3661	
	97	77	0.3112	
Guinea Corn flour	98	78	0.3112	0.2766
	98	74	0.2593	
	98	74	0.2593	
Yam flour	97	80	0.3661	0.3526
	97	79	0.3458	
	97	79	0.3458	

Table 4: K-value for mixture of powered food products

-Specimen	T ₁ (°C) Temperature of Steam chest	T ₂ (°C) Temperature of Brass plate disc C	K Thermal Conductivity (W/m°C)
Rice and Beans	97	74	0.2706
Yam and Cassava	97	78	0.3112
Cassava and Guinea corn	97	76	0.2964

Figure 3: Thermal conductivity of granular food products. Where 1= Rice flour; 2 = Cassava Flour, 3 = Maize, Flour, 4 = Beans Flour, 5 = Guinea Corn flour, 6 = Yam flour

Figure 4: Thermal conductivity of the mixture of granular food products Where 1= Rice and beans flour, 2= Yam and cassava flour and 3= Cassava and guinea corn flour.

Figure 5: Typical Thermal conductivity of two granular food products and their mixture.

Where 1= Rice flour, 2= Beans flour and 3 = Mixture of rice and beans flour

CONCLUSION

The results obtained from this experimental study compare reasonably well within the limit of experimental error with available data on thermal property of the investigated food products. This study thus provides the thermodynamic data on thermal conductivities of some locally grown Nigerian foodstuffs in flour form for further industrial usage and engineering applications. The average thermal conductivity (K - values) obtained was higher for the finer flour. Also, the K- values of the mixtures are characteristically lower compared to at least one of the individual constituents.

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Corresponding Author:

Ogunleye, I.O.

Department of Mechanical Engineering

University of Ado Ekiti, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

E –mail: fccadoekiti@yahoo.com